

COMPOSITION AND PROPERTIES OF NAPHTHA THAT THE MAIN RAW MATERIAL OF THE PETROCHEMICAL INDUSTRY

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Annotation: Naphtha is usually classified as light, intermediate and heavy naphtha. Visbreaking, fluid catalytic cracking, hydrocracking and coking processes play important role in the way producing naphtha. The given table below illustrates important characteristics of naphtha fractions from different crudes. The extracted aromatic fraction of naphtha can be used in the manufacture of synthetic fibers. Naphtha is a complex mixture of hydrocarbons that two types of analyses are usually carried out. The naphtha is used in fertilizer and petrochemical industries and as gasoline. In addition, it is clearly seen from the article that important characteristics of Naphtha, types of hydrocarbon in Naphtha and, hydrocarbon type composition of Naphtha

Key words: naphtha, atmospheric distillation, visbreaking, fluid catalytic cracking, hydrocracking, hydrocarbon, feedstock

Naphtha is a generic name given to light hydrocarbons boiling in the gasoline range. It is a light distillate obtained from refining of crude oil. The boiling ranges of various types of naphtha produced include: C5 - 85°C, C5 - 110°C, C5 - 140°C, C5 - 160°C, C5 - 175°C and C5 - 200°C. In these initial boiling point (IBP) is constant. Other boiling ranges can be 60 - 85°C, 85 - 110°C, and 110 - 140°C. Naphtha is usually classified as light, intermediate and heavy naphtha. If the naphtha fraction boils below 100°C, it is classified as light naphtha. Heavy naphtha boils above 150°C. For intermediate naphtha the boiling range lies between 100 and

150°C.

Naphtha is produced by atmospheric distillation of crude oil. This is called straight-run naphtha. Several conversion processes such as visbreaking, fluid catalytic cracking, hydrocracking, coking also produce naphtha. These are called cracked naphtha.

The important characteristics of naphtha fractions from different crudes are given in Table 1. The proper quality of naphtha for the petrochemical and the fertilizer industry can be achieved by dearomatizing the naphtha with or without reforming operations prior to extraction of aromatics. High aromatic naphtha is not only a nuisance to these industries, but also consumes extra energy in the cracking operations without giving any useful products. Also, it produces more coke and increases the downtime in both the petrochemical and fertilizer industries. On the other hand, the extracted aromatic fraction can be used in the manufacture of synthetic fibers.

Naphtha is a complex mixture of hydrocarbons. Its composition depends on the crude oil processed and the conversion process employed. For the composition of naphtha, two types of analyses are usually carried out. These are:

- Hydrocarbon type analysis
- Individual component wise analysis

The hydrocarbon type analysis determines the percentage of paraffins, olefins, naphthenes and aromatics. Different types of compounds found in naphtha fractions for various uses are given in Table 2. The approximate carbon number range of the products is also given in the same table. In Table 3., a summary of quality of the naphtha fractions from various indigenous and certain imported and worldwide available crudes with respect to the paraf- fin/naphthene/aromatic contents of their naphtha fractions are given. The value indicated is for the full range naphtha (C5 - 140°C).

Naphtha finds an extensive use as fertilizer feedstock where it is steam reformed to give synthesis gas, the starting material for fertilizers. Crudes which

yield full range naphtha of high aromatic content of more than 10-12 percent aromatics are available and can be used by the fertilizer industry.

In petrochemical industry, naphtha (C5 - 140°C) is used as feedstock for steam crackers, producing hydrogen, methane, ethylene, propylene, the butenes, butadiene and to a lesser extent benzene and isoprene. These are the raw material for large number of petrochemicals. The petrochemical industry needs crude with as little aromatics percentage as possible with 4-6 percent as a ‘benchmark’ naphtha as per the supplies available in the past from the Ankaleshwar crude and from the imported Middle East crudes. The condensates (from LPG extraction in natural gas plants) and the reformer raffinates can supply only a fraction (about 25 percent) of the total naphtha requirement of the petrochemical industry.

Catalytic reforming of straight-run naphtha yields a CG - Cs reformat rich in the aromatic hydrocarbons, benzene, toluene, ethylbenzene and the xylenes. The raffinate remaining after recovery of the aromatic hydrocarbons is sometimes used to augment straight-run naphtha as a steam-cracker feedstock. Naphtha-range products from hydrocracking of heavier oil fractions are also very occasionally used as steam-cracker feed stocks.

The steam-cracker feedstock is vaporized and steam is added in a ratio of about 0.3-0.5 tonne of steam per tonne of naphtha. The mixture is heated rapidly to the cracking temperature through tubular coils inside an oil- or gas-fired furnace. The temperature of operation varies from 750°C for medium/low severity to 900°C for high severity. To obtain the best yield of ethylene an important factor is a very short residence time, e.g. 0.25 s. This reduces the amount of coke produced. Longer residence time, e.g. 0.6 s, at low/medium severity increases the yield of aromatics.

The use of naphtha as gasoline requires its high antiknock value or octane number. Depending on the crude source, the octane number of straight-run naphtha varies in the range of 50-70.

Table 1. Important Characteristics of Naphthas from Different Crudes

Sl. No	Charac-teristics	Aghajari (34.3° API)		Light Arabian (34.5° API)		Kuwait (31.5° API)		Murban (39.3° API)		Darius (34° API)									
		C ₅ - 175°C	C ₅ - 200°C	C ₅ -175°C	C ₅ -200°C	C ₅ - 175°C	C ₅ - 200°C	C ₅ - 175°C	C ₅ - 200°C	C ₅ - 175°C	C ₅ - 200°C								
1	Gravity 15/15°C	0.73	0.74	0.72	0.735	0.72	0.730	0.73	0.74	0.718	0.727								
2	Yield on crude, wt. %	20.45	24.80	19.80	25.4	15.9	19.9	24.5	30.17	21	25								
3	Sulphur, wt. %	0.096	0.101	0.03	0.04	0.044	0.075	0.018	0.022	0.08	0.103								
4	Total mer-captans, wt. %	0.0412	0.0356	0.00019	0.00016	0.015	0.014	0.013	0.013	-	-								
5	C/H ratio	5.64	5.68	5.84	5.97	5.72	5.75	6.1	6.2	5.56	5.62								
6	PONA*, vol. %	55.2	53.0	71.5	68.0	-	-	67.0	64.0	78.0	75.0								
												29.0	30.6	20.0	20.0	18.0	19.0	14.0	15

	Charac- teristics	Aghajari		Light Arabian		Kuwait		Murban		Darius	
		(34.3 ^o API)		(34.5 ^o API)		(31.5 ^o API)		(39.3 ^o API)		(34 ^o API)	
		C ₅ – 175 ^o C	C ₅ – 200 ^o C	C ₅ – 175 ^o C	C ₅ – 200 ^o C	C ₅ – 175 ^o C	C ₅ – 200 ^o C	C ₅ – 175 ^o C	C ₅ – 200 ^o C	C ₅ – 175 ^o C	C ₅ – 200 ^o C
1	Gravity 15/15 ^o C	0.73	0.74	0.72	0.735	0.72	0.73 0	0.73	0.74	0.71 8	0.72 7
2	Yield on crude, wt.%	20.45	24.80	19.80	25.4	15.9	19.9	24.5	30.1 7	21	25
3	Sulphur, wt.%	0.096	0.101	0.03	0.04	0.04 4	0.07 5	0.01 8	0.02 2	0.08	0.10 3
4	Total mer- captans, wt,%	0.041 2	0.035 6	0.000 19	0.000 16	0.01 5	0.01 4	0.01 3	0.01 3	-	-
5	C/H ratio	5.64	5.68	5.84	5.97	5.72	5.75	6.1	6.2	5.56	5.62
6	PONA*,vol . % P N A	55.2 29.0 15.8	53.0 30.6 16.4	71.5 20.0 19.5	68.0 20.0 12.0	- - 7.0	- - 9.0	67.0 18.0 15.0	64.0 19.0 17.0	78.0 14.0 8.0	75.0 15 10.0

Table 2. Types of Hydrocarbon in Naphthas

No. of atoms	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13
Boiling point, ^o C	36	69	98	126	151	174	196	216	235
Types of compounds found									
Normal paraffins	P*	P	P	P	P	P	P	P	P
Branched paraffins	P	P	P	P	P	P	P	P	P

Saturated cyclic	P	P	P	P	P	P	P	P	P
Aromatics-Mono	-	P	P	P	P	P	P	P	P
Aromatics-Di	-	-	-	-	-	P	P	P	P
Aromatic naphthenes	-	-	-	-	P	P	P	P	P
Aromatic nonhydrocarbons	P	P	P	P	P	P	P	P	P
Aromatic olefins	-	-	-	PC	PC	PC	PC	PC	PC
Olefins cyclic	PC ⁺	PC	PC	PC	PC	PC	PC	PC	PC
Approximate carbon number range of products	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13
Ligroin	_____								
Precipitation naphtha		_____							
VM&P naphtha			_____						
Mineral spirits					_____				
Gasoline	_____								
Kerosene					_____				
Jet fuels					_____				
Petrochemical feedstocks	_____								

*P-Present, +PC-Present in cracked naphtha only

Table 3. Hydrocarbon Type Composition of Naphthas

<i>Crude</i>	Composition of naphtha (C ₅ -140°C)		
	<i>Paraffin</i>	<i>Naphthene</i>	<i>Aromatic</i>
Assam (Mix.), vol.%	32-40	52-43	16-17
North Gujarat, vol.%	52.5	42	5.5
Ankaleshwar, vol.%	70.8	25	4.2
Bombey High, vol.%	53.7	25	21.3
Iranian Light, wt.%	57.5	31.1	11.4
Iranian Heavy, wt.%	53.4	33.1	13.5
Basrah, vol.%	68.5	18.8	12.7

Kirkud blend, vol.%	67.5	22	10.5
Heavy Maya, vol.%	60.6	27	12.4
North Sea, wt.%	59	33	8
Russia export blend, wt.%	38.5	52	9.5

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